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In-situ Deep Learning for Prediction and Controls in Smart Composites

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#ICCM22

Motivation: Composites with sensors, actuators and computers

Smarter structural health monitoring systems

Morphing wings

We want composites that can react to physical interactions with their environment through computations performed within the material

Challenges

1. Manufacturing

Chang group
Stanford

Shepherd group
Cornell

Keplinger group
CU Boulder

Lewis/Wood groups
Harvard

2. Communication

3. Computation

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Towards more **Localized** Computation

Microcontrollers as data collectors and pre-processors

Microcontrollers as intelligent decision-making or prediction devices

Computational Platform

- ESP32 system-on-a-chip: computer with wireless communication
- 160Mhz, 512kB RAM, real time OS
- Sparkfun break-out board for easy experimentation
- Powerful enough to run deep learning networks trained by TensorFlow using *nn4mc*

<https://github.com/correllab/nn4mc>

Case 1: Centralized vs. edge computing for impact source localization

Aguasvivas et al. Wireless Online Impact Source Localization on a Composite. Procedia Manufacturing 24, 319-324.

Case 1: Limitations

- Difficult to setup the model for different shapes
- Boundary conditions affect signal propagation
- Accuracy of manufacturing matters
- Computers need to be synchronized
- Hand-coding of signal processing algorithms generally difficult

Proposed Approach

Embedded Neural Network for Online Regression

Online Errors vs. Testing Set Errors

Overall Experiment		
Parameter	Testing Set Error	Online Error
r [cm]	-0.716 ± 3.9	2.264 ± 1.384
θ [rad]	-0.027 ± 0.56	0.758 ± 0.543

center of sensor node

	Results at Specific Test Points									
	{0, 0}		{10, 145}		{7.5, 180}		{9, 0}		{6.5, 90}	
	r	theta	r	theta	r	theta	r	theta	r	theta
Mean Error	2.741	0.290	0.304	1.059	2.257	1.269	3.135	0.631	2.884	0.542
Standard Error	2.993	0.463	0.369	0.610	0.524	0.688	1.975	0.547	1.061	0.407

Best case in hand-coded algorithm (planar): 4.5 cm
Better online results than with hand-coding solutions!

Case 2: Control

- 3 Actuators (angle, twist, distance)
- 12 optical sensors to measure stretch (randomly deployed)

Testing Set Neural Network Predicted States

Raw data

Neural network is capable of predicting future servo states based on current sensor signal and current control actions

Can we use this model to control the actuators?

- We set a target state for each servo
- We expect the simulated servo to meet this target in steady state using learned model
- Corrections are made through a P-controller applied to predictions 10 timesteps ahead

Simulated control on 100 Monte Carlo generated initial states for twist control servo and blocker distance

Conclusions

- Machine learning can automatically learn input/output relationships for a number of smart composite case studies
- The more sensing data, the better
- Accurate placement does not matter
- State-of-the-art microcontrollers are powerful enough to execute neural network predictions
- Strong potential for embedded control

References

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Supplementary Slides

Sample recordings for different radii and angles

- Differentiable patterns depending on r and θ
- No need for additional communication for triangulation at a single sensor node
- Increased dimensionality of the features

Errors on Neural Network Predictions of States

Error on Testing Set Neural Network Predictions

Errors in neural network predictions on testing set data are relatively low with around 9 degrees offset for twist control servo angle and worst case 0.075 cm for block distance